

New Education Policy 2020 and Children with Disability

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Abstract: A large part of the youth population in India is suffering from single or multiple disabilities. It is often difficult for them to take their place in society. Education, health, and employment are a few challenges they face in daily life. The government brings policies, programs, and provisions from time to time for their well-being. Moving forward in this direction, the government announced the new education policy on 29 July 2020, which includes actions for the holistic development of the disabled. New Education Policy 2020 opens a new era in educational reform. This policy includes guidelines for “Equal opportunity” and “Barrier-free Education” for the well-being of the disabled. This article has been presented in the context of NEP 2020 and children with disabilities. Researchers have presented some suggestions in this paper, which can prove beneficial in future for disabled children.

Key Words - New Education Policy, Disability, Children with disability, Importance.

The Indian national education policy was first introduced in 1986, which was later amended in 1992. Since then, there were many changes in society and education, which constantly demanded amendments in the education policy. Therefore, the new education policy 2020 was introduced on 29th July 2020. This policy replaced 34 years old Indian national education policy. The education policy provides measures for foundational pillars of equality, quality, access, affordability, and accountability. The new policy provides instructions for equal opportunity and education to children with disabilities. The barrier-free education and access to education for children with disabilities were important provisions in the new educational policy 2020. According to Merriam-Webster “Disability is a physical, mental, cognitive, or developmental condition that impairs, interferes with, or limits a person’s ability to engage in certain tasks or actions or participate in typical daily activities and interactions.”

Objective of the Study-

- 1- To individual development of disabled child.
- 2- To Providing opportunities for "Barrier Free Education" to all children with disabilities.
- 2- To achievement of national goal.
- 3- To bringing out the hidden talent in the child.
- 4- To achieving the goal of the national Education Policy.
- 5- To Bringing positivity in the relationship between the society, the disabled family and stakeholder.

Key Points of the New Education Policy 2020-

There are the main key points-

- NEP 2020, adopted on 29th July 2020.

- NEP 2020 which will replace the existing 10+2 school system with a new 5+3+3+4 school system.
- Ensuring Universal Access at all levels of school education.
- Early Childhood Care & Education with new Curricular and Pedagogical Structure.
- This policy for “Equal opportunity” and “Barrier-free Education” for the well-being of the disabled.
- Attaining Foundational Literacy and Numeracy.
- Reforms in school curricula and pedagogy.
- Multilingualism and the power of language.
- The aim of the new policy 2020 is the universalize of education from pre-school to secondary level with 100% Gross Enrolment Ratio ((GER) in school education policy 2030.
- Now the age group for the Right to Education (RTE) is now 3 to 8 years (earlier 14 years.)
- This education policy describes the much-awaited new reforms that the country and society have needed for a long time. This adaptation can be visible or beneficial for children with disabilities and other disabled stakeholders. Therefore, disabled children's methods of learning, teaching pedagogy, and teachers' ability are important concerns in this policy.
- PWD act 2016 has been kept in mind to provide barrier-free education to disabled children. Generally, children with

disabilities face barriers to access to education in preschool and primary school. Because studies find that some schools have less than 40% stairs and 17% have almost accessible toilets. Apart from this many other facilities related to disability are also not available in those schools.

Importance of NEP 2020 for Disabled Child-

Here some importance points-

- It speculates an India-centric education system and the provision of quality education and equitable access to all students in a sustainable manner.
- It allows the students to enjoy the education and gain confidence due to individual learning or the personal growth and development of the special children.
- According NEP 2020 will bring 2 crores out of school children back into the mainstream, through the open schooling system.
- The disability cases could include different variety like-emotional, mental, physical developmental.
- Under NEP recognizes the importance of creating enabling mechanisms for providing Children with Special Needs (CWSN) or Disabled.
- This policy promotes inclusive education and provides equal education to both. Normal children and children with disabilities.
- New Education Policy 2020 is an important attempt to provide "barrier-free education" to the disabled and also a concrete step toward bringing them into the "mainstream" education.
- New Education Policy 2020 aims to ensure that no child from birth misses an opportunity to read, write and excel that's why this new policy will lay special emphasis on disabled children.
- Under NEP 2020, it will be possible to provide resources for the inclusion of children with disabilities in the school and school premises, as well as assist in the appointment of trained special teachers to teach such students.
- This policy promotes inclusive education and provides equal education to both normal and children with disabilities.
- It will enable children with disabilities to fully participate in the regular schooling process from basic to the higher levels of education. It also includes providing cross-disability training with appropriate technology-based equipment and support mechanisms. The support of teachers will also be included according to the need of these children.
- The knowledge about teaching children with specific disabilities will be an integral part of all teacher education programs.
- There will be no discrimination in schools.
- Accessible school infrastructure, reasonable accommodation, personal support, and teaching with Braille and Indian sign language.
- School infrastructure can be used as free social consciousness centers.
- Recruitment of special teachers with cross-disability training.
- Disability awareness has been included in teacher education.
- Resources will be provided to school campuses for the integration of children with disabilities, along with the assistive devices, and teaching and learning materials.
- The home-based education will continue to be an option for children who are unable to attend school. They will be treated like other children based on the normal system.
- Special attention will be given to the safety and security of children with disabilities.
- Schools will be provided with assistive devices, suitable technology-based tools, and language-appropriate teaching-learning materials to facilitate the changes among children with disabilities.
- While preparing the National Curriculum Framework (NCF) for children with disabilities, NCERT will ensure that it consults expert and experienced persons with the national institute of DEPWDs.
- In addition, a high-quality module will also be developed for NIOS (National Indian Open School) to teach Indian sign language and other basic subjects using Indian sign language.
- Each state will be encouraged to set up "BAL-BHAWAN" in the district. To build the future of these disabled children, their

career-related, sports-related, and other interest-related activities will be addressed.

- Based on this policy, it has also been taken care of that child with benchmark disabilities have the option of regular or special school education as per RPWD Act 2016, (As per Section 2(r) of the Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act 2016. A person with a benchmark disability means a person having a specified disability of not less than forty percent (40%) as certified by the Certifying Authority). The resource centers with special teachers and trainers will be set up for different types of children with disabilities and will be made available to meet the rehabilitation and educational requirements of these children.
- Attention has also been given to women and transgender disabled students. An additional and necessary fund will be given to the states to build toilets for them, keep them clean, and provide bicycles and cash transfers.
- Evaluation and certification agency will continue to function for transparency. The new National Assessment Center PARAKH will prepare guidelines for assessment from the basic level to the higher education level to ensure equitable access and opportunities for all learning students.
- Barrier-free education will be main objective of the government, provided to all disabled children.

Conclusion-

New Education Policy 2020 developed according to the demands of the 21st century; it is very important step for all round development of Indian country and society. In which special attention has been given to children with disabilities along with normal children. Therefore, to fulfill this need, a comprehensive national education policy has been formulated by the nation. This will lead to the welfare and well being of the country along with the education system. It is step towards bringing them into the "mainstream" education.

In the end, it can be said that these reforms/changes will help in providing quality education and ensures well-being of the children with disabilities. All these features are under the pre-planned program of the government of India. It is a great move and hopes it goes well. The

researcher tried to highlight some important points on India's New Education Policy 2020 and Disabled students in this research paper.

Suggestions/Recommendations-

On the basis of many studies, the researcher has presented some suggestions for making children with disabilities prosperous and well-being, which can definitely prove useful in making their future bright.

1-The policy and provisions for the Welfare of children with disabilities should be properly implemented on the basis of NEP 2020 proposed by the government.

2-To facilitate the education of children with disabilities, schools should be provided with assistive devices, suitable Technology based equipment, and language-appropriate learning materials.

3-With regards to the modules developed to improve language quality, the government should ensure that it reaches every child with disabilities.

4-In relation to many policies and provisions proposed by the government, it is the duty of the central and state government as well as the local government and NGOs to make observations and help from time to time for the Welfare of these children.

5-The teacher must be 100% trained to teach handicapped children or only trained teachers should be hired in special or inclusive schools.

6- Any general School, inclusive school, or special school must admit the child on the basis of his/her uniqueness.

7- According to the policy, there is no separation in the stream of Science, Arts, and Commerce so the child who wants to stream admission in any stream must give admission on the basis of his merit or ability.

8-Schools should have the freedom to modify the structure of the school curriculum based on the interest and needs of the children.

9- It is the duty of the school and the teacher to try that the dropout of the child is minimized.

10- For the development of children, schools should ensure that they have sports material playgrounds and sports teachers.

11- Schools should ensure a healthy and fun-filled environment is available for the all-around development of the children.

12- It is the ultimate duty of every teacher to understand the attitude of the child and motivate him to do any work on the basis of that.

13- It is the duty of the teacher and the school that if the child is interested in any extracurricular activities more than the standard studies then they should be supported.

14- Society should support any handicapped/disabled child and their parents and not look at them with an inferiority complex.

15- Family society and school all together should always motivate the disabled child that he is the best as he is.

16- Based on the demand of the present circumstances, Science and Technology should be developed for handicapped children. So that they can contribute to building themselves and the nation.

17- Through policies and programs for the welfare of children, government and non-government organizations should help.

18- The NEP 2020 is a huge stride in the right direction — it focuses on the holistic development of students by ensuring access, relevance, equity, quality, and strong foundational learning. The new policy has numerous takeaways for education sector stakeholders.

19- The NEP 2020 seeks to “ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all” by 2030. This is NEP 2020 goal with India's learning outcomes. It has drawn much attention to the theme of inclusive and equitable education. 20- The government should strictly implement “Barrier Free Education” for the well being and development of children with disabilities.

I hope that the suggestions given by researchers regarding the new education policy and disabled children will definitely be beneficial for the students, teachers and family. Best wishes to all for the future. Thanks....

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